

Peer-to-Peer Platform for Corona-related Workforce

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Plattform	Domain	Beschreibung	Bewertung trusted.d	Estimated Number of Users / Questions	since when	sector / focus	business model	Country
Stack Overflow	https://stackoverflow.com/	Stack Overflow is an open community for anyone that codes. We help you get answers to your toughest coding questions, share knowledge with your coworkers in private, and find your next dream job.	2.1 von 5	10.000.000	2008	Coding	Charging money for posting jobs on their job exchange	USA
Mathefrage.de	https://mathefragen.de/	A tool for learning and helping to bring them together for learning in the best possible way. The portal is constantly being further developed and features are added to optimize the learning process. In addition, the goal is to evaluate learning data regarding when, how and with which method is asked and helped in order to individualize the learning process.	Keine Bewertung	18.000	2018	Math	Charging money for posting jobs on their job exchange	DE
GitHub	https://github.com/	GitHub provides code hosting services that allow developers/people to build software for open source and private projects in organizations. It designs and develops an online platform to allow users to store and share codes repositories with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers.	4 von 5	40.000.000	2008	Coding / Hosting	Subscription fees	USA
PatientsLikeMe	https://www.patientslikeme.com/	PatientsLikeMe, the world's largest personalized health network, helps people find new options for treatments, connect with others, and take action to improve their outcomes. The company has worked with every major pharmaceutical company and a range of government organizations to bring the patient voice to research, development and public policy. With more than 600,000 members, PatientsLikeMe is a trusted source for real-world disease information and a clinically robust resource that has published more than 100 research studies.	Keine Bewertung	600.000	2004	Health	Selling customer data to pharmaceutical companies	USA
Sermo	https://www.sermo.com/about/	The most popular site for healthcare providers on the web today. Sermo is focused on connecting "verified and credentialed" physicians from around the world in 150 countries, with plans to expand even further globally. Doctors can ask their peers anonymous questions regarding patient care in this "virtual doctors lounge". Currently the site has over 800,000 users.	Keine Bewertung	800.000	2005	Health	Healthcare institutions, financial services firms and government agencies purchase SERMO products to access this elite group of practitioners.	USA
Figure1	https://www.figure1.com/	This resource allows healthcare providers from around the world to share anonymous images of an ailment, such as x-rays, and compare them to other images available on the site. This tool is particularly useful for doctors in remote locations who may be treating a patient with a rare disorder. With millions of healthcare providers participating, it's become one of the largest digital platforms for medical professionals and an invaluable tool for saving lives.	Keine Bewertung	1.000.000	2012	Health - "Like Instagram for doctors"	Sponsored content and polls	USA
Daily Rounds	https://www.dailyrounds.org/	Available on desktop, Android and iOS, DailyRounds is a community of international physicians that's around 30,000 strong. The platform allows physicians to engage in chat, share medical expertise, load case files and access a drug database. It's a one stop network for physicians looking for professional advice and camaraderie.	Keine Bewertung	30.000	2013	Health	Offer medical apps for special cases	India

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